

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ORGANIZATIONAL SILENCE AS A PREDICTORS OF WORKPLACE BULLYING AMONG NURSES IN SOUTH-WEST NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated antecedents and consequences of workplace bullying among nurses in Hospitals in South-West Nigeria. Essentially, bullying at workplace has been seen a hot topic discussed frequently throughout the developed world. The study utilized an *Ex-Post Facto* Design which is suitable for investigating variables where manipulation is not ethical and particularly appropriate for examining the influence of organizational silence on workplace bullying among nurses in South –West Nigeria.

The findings of the study revealed that the tested hypothesis indicated that a significant prediction of workplace bullying by the organizational silence variable. The F-statistic of $F(1, 418) = 114.258, P < .05; R = .22$.

The study concluded that organizational silence significantly predicted workplace bullying among nurses in South-West Nigeria.

Keywords: Organizational Silence, Workplace Bullying, Nurses, South-West.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, the phenomenon of workplace bullying has been conceptualized and studied using various terminologies, reflecting its complex and multifaceted nature. Terms such as "mobbing" (Leymann, 1990) and "harassment" (Bjorkqvist, et al., 1994) are commonly used in Europe, while "workplace aggression" is prevalent in American literature (Baron & Neuman, 1998). In Australia and the United Kingdom, "workplace bullying" is widely adopted to describe persistent negative behaviors aimed at undermining individuals or groups (Einarsen & Skogstad, 1996). While terminologies vary, they converge on characteristics of bullying: repetition, intentionality, and a power imbalance between the perpetrator and the target.

Nurses in Nigeria are particularly vulnerable to workplace bullying due to the demanding nature of their profession. As the backbone of healthcare delivery, nurses perform critical roles that require constant interaction with patients, families, and colleagues under often stressful and resource-limited conditions. These challenges are exacerbated by systemic issues, including poor staffing ratios, inadequate managerial support, and limited access to resources, which can fuel interpersonal conflicts and toxic workplace behaviors (Hutchinson, et al., 2010; Kivimaki, et al., 2003).

At the organizational level, workplace bullying contributes to increased absenteeism, higher turnover rates, and reduced job satisfaction, all of which undermine workforce stability and productivity. Studies have shown that nurses exposed to bullying are more likely

to exhibit symptoms of burnout, characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a diminished sense of personal accomplishment (Laschinger & Grau, 2012). These outcomes not only compromise patient care but also place additional strain on an already overburdened healthcare system, with cascading effects on patient outcomes and organizational performance (Houck, et al., 2017).

Despite the global recognition of workplace bullying, its prevalence and impact within Nigerian healthcare settings remain underexplored. Studies from other countries suggest that up to 40% of nurses experience workplace bullying (Trépanier, et al., 2019), with healthcare workers being particularly vulnerable due to the high-stress nature of their work. In Nigeria, the situation is likely exacerbated by systemic challenges, including underfunded healthcare facilities, high patient-to-nurse ratios, and cultural attitudes that may tolerate or even encourage hierarchical bullying.

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The hierarchical structure of healthcare institutions further exacerbates the issue. Nurses, particularly junior staff, often find themselves at the lower end of workplace power dynamics, making them susceptible to bullying by senior colleagues, supervisors and even patients. Power imbalances within these structures create an environment where bullying is normalized or dismissed as a means of "discipline" or "management" (Hutchinson, et al., 2006). In such environments, bullying behaviors may range from overt actions like verbal abuse and excessive criticism to covert acts such as exclusion from team activities or deliberate withholding of essential information.

Statement of the Problem

Workplace bullying is a prevalent psychological issue associated with various workplaces worldwide, and it remains a significant concern in healthcare settings. The healthcare sector, particularly nursing, is crucial to any nation's development, and nurses represent the largest group of healthcare professionals. Despite their essential role in delivering healthcare services, nurses are often subjected to various forms of bullying, including verbal abuse, social exclusion, and professional undermining. These behaviors not only adversely affect individual nurses but also have a profound impact on the healthcare system. The consequences of bullying in nursing are far-reaching, affecting nurses' psychological and physical health, job performance, and ultimately the quality of patient care (Favaro, et al., 2021; Elazzazy, 2023).

In healthcare settings such as Hospitals, bullying can take various forms, from overt actions such as verbal abuse and physical aggression to more covert behaviors like social isolation and undermining professional competence. Workplace bullying has been shown to lead to serious psychological distress, including anxiety, depression, burnout, and physical health problems such as headaches, gastrointestinal issues, and cardiovascular problems (Einarsen, et al., 2011; Hayes, et al., 2012). In the context of healthcare, bullying has significant organizational consequences, including increased turnover, absenteeism, and diminished work engagement, all of which hinder the effectiveness of healthcare delivery and increase costs for healthcare organizations (Clausen, Høgh, & Borg, 2012; Nielsen, et al., 2017).

Antecedents of workplace bullying refer to the factors or events that contribute to its occurrence, while consequences refer to the outcomes or effects of the

bullying behavior. In the Nigerian healthcare sector, which is already under significant strain due to limited resources, high patient-to-nurse ratios, and other systemic challenges, the added burden of workplace bullying exacerbates these issues. It contributes to high levels of stress, burnout, and turnover among nurses, further weakening the healthcare system (Kivimaki, et al., 2003; Trépanier, et al., 2019). Understanding the antecedents and consequences of workplace bullying among nurses is essential to developing effective strategies for both prevention and intervention in Nigerian healthcare settings.

Research has indicated that lack of organizational support, high workload, and poor communication can contribute to a culture of bullying within healthcare settings. Nurses who feel overworked, unsupported, or undervalued are more likely to engage in bullying behavior toward their colleagues as a way of coping with stress and frustration (Golparvar, et al., 2012). Moreover, the hierarchical nature of healthcare institutions can exacerbate power imbalances, enabling senior nurses or administrators to intimidate and belittle junior staff (Leong & Crossman, 2017). This culture of bullying is not only detrimental to individual nurses but also has profound implications for the overall functioning of healthcare organizations.

Western scholars, such as Einarsen et al. (2011), have highlighted that nurses who experience bullying are more likely to suffer from anxiety, depression, and burnout, as well as physical health problems, including headaches, gastrointestinal issues, and cardiovascular problems. Workplace bullying also imposes significant costs on healthcare organizations, including increased turnover (Hayes, et al., 2012), sickness absence (Clausen, Høgh, & Borg, 2012), and disability retirement (Nielsen, et al., 2017, as cited in Conway, et al., 2021). These costs not only undermine the financial health of healthcare organizations but also contribute to a strained work environment, ultimately compromising patient care.

The problem of workplace bullying is further exacerbated by ineffective Human Resource Management (HRM) practices in many healthcare institutions. Inconsistent or non-existent policies on workplace bullying, a lack of training for staff on conflict resolution, and insufficient support for victims create an environment where bullying can thrive. These deficiencies in HRM practices fail to protect nurses and also hinder the overall effectiveness of healthcare delivery. HRM practices that are proactive in addressing bullying, such as clear anti-bullying policies, conflict management training, and robust support systems for victims, are critical for reducing workplace bullying and improving the healthcare environment (Castronova, Pullizzi, & Evans, 2016; Goh, Hosier, & Zhang, 2022).

Identifying the antecedents of workplace bullying is essential for developing preventive strategies aimed at addressing the issue and mitigating its adverse impact on both nurses' mental health and organizational productivity. Furthermore, understanding the consequences of workplace bullying will inform interventions that can improve nurses' well-being, reduce turnover, and enhance patient care outcomes (Rutherford,

Gillespie, & Smith, 2019; Pfeifer & Vessey, 2017). The results of this study are expected to provide valuable insights into how HRM practices can be used to combat workplace bullying and improve the work environment for nurses in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The research question below has been developed to guide this study and address the core objectives of understanding the organizational silence as a predictor of workplace bullying among nurses in hospital in South-West Nigeria.

i. To what extent will organizational silence show independent prediction of workplace bullying experience among nurses in hospital in South-West, Nigeria?

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to:

- assess the independent prediction of workplace bullying experience by organizational silence among nurses in hospital in South-West, Nigeria;

Research Hypothesis

Organizational Silence will show independent prediction of workplace bullying experience among nurses in hospital in South-West, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Concept of Bullying

Bullying is a multifaceted phenomenon characterized by repeated negative actions directed toward an individual, resulting in harm, distress, or discomfort. In general, bullying involves an imbalance of power, where the perpetrator exerts control over the victim through intimidation, humiliation, or aggression (Einarsen, et al, 2011). The World Health Organization (WHO) defines bullying as “the repeated exposure, over time, to negative actions on the part of one or more other persons” (WHO, 2020). Similarly, the International Labour Organization (ILO) describes bullying as “offensive behavior through vindictive, cruel, malicious, or humiliating attempts to undermine an individual or group of employees” (ILO, 2019). Bullying can take various forms, including physical, verbal, relational, psychological, and cyberbullying (Olweus, 1993; Farley, et al., 2016).

Physical Bullying

Physical bullying involves acts of aggression that cause harm or threaten harm, such as hitting, pushing, or other physical attacks. While physical bullying is often easier to identify due to its overt nature, it can have severe long-term effects on both the physical and emotional well-being of the victim. For instance, in Nigerian healthcare settings, physical bullying might manifest when senior staff physically intimidate junior nurses, potentially leading to both psychological trauma and physical harm (Adebayo, Olatunji, & Awoniyi, 2021). This type of bullying is more obvious but can still have lasting consequences for nurses who experience it.

Verbal Bullying

Verbal bullying consists of derogatory comments, name-calling, and other persistent negative remarks designed to humiliate or degrade the victim. This form of bullying can be just as damaging, if not more so, than

physical bullying, as it directly attacks the victim’s self-esteem and mental health. In Nigerian hospitals, verbal bullying often occurs in hierarchical environments where junior nurses are publicly belittled by supervisors or patients, creating an atmosphere of fear and humiliation. Such verbal abuse can significantly diminish a nurse’s self-worth and lead to long-term emotional distress (Smith & Thompson, 2021).

Relational Bullying

Relational bullying, also known as relational aggression or social bullying, involves actions aimed at harming a person’s social relationships or reputation. It can include spreading rumors, deliberately excluding individuals from social or work-related groups, and publicly embarrassing or humiliating the victim. In Nigerian healthcare settings, relational bullying may manifest when experienced nurses deliberately exclude new or younger nurses from social gatherings or collaborative work environments, harming the victim’s reputation and career prospects (Craig & Pepler, 2007). These tactics cause emotional distress and undermine the victim’s social standing, often leading to long-term social and psychological consequences.

Psychological Bullying

Psychological bullying, or emotional bullying, is less overt and often involves subtle tactics such as exclusion, gossip, and persistent undermining of the victim’s confidence. It can be difficult to detect, as it frequently takes the form of passive-aggressive behavior or covert manipulation. In Nigerian healthcare contexts, psychological bullying may occur when colleagues or superiors undermine a nurse’s professional competence through gossip or deliberate exclusion from decision-making processes, which can have devastating effects on the victim’s confidence and mental health (Einarsen, et al., 2020). Research indicates that prolonged exposure to psychological bullying can lead to anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Einarsen, et al., 2020).

Cyberbullying

With the rise of digital communication, workplace bullying can now extend into virtual environments through emails, messaging platforms, or social media. Cyberbullying adds a layer of anonymity, making it harder to trace and even more pervasive. In Nigerian healthcare environments, where digital communication tools are increasingly used to communicate instructions, reports, and feedback, cyberbullying may occur when a nurse is targeted with offensive or humiliating messages online, such as through work-related emails or social media platforms (Farley, et al., 2016). This form of bullying is particularly harmful because it can continue outside of work hours and escalate quickly, often involving many people, making it difficult for victims to escape.

Bullying is an escalating process during which the victim is systematically targeted and placed in a weaker position compared to the perpetrator. As noted by Einarsen, et al. (2011), bullying cannot be considered a one-off event or a conflict between two individuals of equal power. The features of bullying include frequency, persistency, hostility, and power imbalance.

The frequency and persistency of negative acts are critical in distinguishing bullying from isolated incidents or ordinary conflicts (Einarsen, et al., 2011; Francioli, 2014).

Hostility in bullying often manifests as negative acts from colleagues or superiors, where the victim finds it challenging to defend themselves due to the power imbalance between the perpetrator and the victim (Nielsen & Einarsen, 2012). The imbalance of power is not always hierarchical; it can stem from informal sources such as experience or knowledge (Cowie, et al., 2002). In Nigerian hospitals, the power imbalance often exists not only between supervisors and junior staff but also among colleagues, where more experienced nurses may target newer or less experienced staff members.

Another critical characteristic of bullying is its duration. Bullying is defined by its persistent and repeated nature, with negative acts occurring regularly over a period of time (Leymann, 1996). According to Einarsen, et al. (2011), bullying is considered ongoing if it continues for six months or more, though this duration may vary depending on the individual case. The unwanted nature of the behavior is central to its definition, with victims experiencing continuous insults, offensive remarks, and social exclusion, which can significantly impact their work performance and perception of the workplace (Einarsen & Raknes, 1997; Williams, 1997).

The intentional nature of bullying distinguishes it from other types of conflict. While misunderstandings or conflicts may arise unintentionally, bullying is always deliberate, with the perpetrator attempting to harm, belittle, or undermine the victim over time (Volk, et al., 2014). This intentionality is crucial in differentiating bullying from other forms of aggression that are not aimed at establishing dominance. The power imbalance is another feature of bullying, with perpetrators using physical strength, social status, or organizational position to exert control over the victim (Rigby, 2003; Smith, 2016). In Nigerian hospitals, this imbalance often takes the form of supervisors bullying subordinates or colleagues marginalizing others based on factors such as social capital or work position (Hutchinson, et al., 2019).

The long-term consequences of bullying are extensive and can affect not only the victim's immediate well-being but also their mental, emotional, and physical health. Victims often experience anxiety, depression, and reduced self-esteem, and in severe cases, may develop suicidal ideation (Lutgen-Sandvik, et al., 2007). Chronic exposure to bullying can result in lasting psychological trauma and organizational consequences such as increased absenteeism, lower job satisfaction, and higher turnover rates (Einarsen, et al., 2003). In healthcare settings, especially among nurses, bullying can contribute to emotional exhaustion, decreased job satisfaction, and turnover intentions (Hutchinson, et al., 2019). Understanding the various forms of bullying and their impact is essential for developing effective interventions to create safer, more supportive workplace environments.

Workplace bullying has increasingly become a topic of interest within organizational studies, particularly in high-stress professions like nursing. Defined broadly, workplace bullying involves repeated, long-term abusive behaviors towards employees, resulting in negative psychological, physical, and occupational outcomes (Einarsen, et al., 2011). In healthcare settings, where stress levels are often elevated due to the demanding nature of the work, nurses are particularly vulnerable to bullying. This is concerning not only because of the personal impact on victims but also due to the broader consequences for healthcare organizations, including reduced job satisfaction, high turnover rates, and diminished quality of care (Hutchinson, et al., 2010). In Nigeria, the healthcare system faces numerous challenges, including understaffing, inadequate resources, and organizational inefficiencies, all of which can exacerbate stressful working conditions and contribute to workplace bullying (Adebayo, et al., 2021).

Concept of Workplace Bullying

Definition of Workplace Bullying

Workplace bullying refers to the persistent, intentional mistreatment of an individual in a professional setting, resulting in physical, psychological, or emotional harm. It is characterized by repeated hostile actions that can take various forms, including verbal abuse, non-verbal hostility, and social isolation.

According to Einarsen et al. (2011), workplace bullying is defined as "harassing, offending, or socially excluding someone at work or negatively affecting their work tasks repeatedly and regularly, over a period of time, where the bullied individual finds it difficult to defend themselves." This definition emphasizes the repetitive nature of the behavior and the power imbalance that often makes it difficult for victims to resist or seek help. Similarly, the International Labour Organization (ILO) (2020) expands this definition to include behaviors like belittling, undermining, and spreading rumors, which can occur between peers or involve supervisors and subordinates.

Power Dynamics in the Workplace

A core characteristic of workplace bullying is the power imbalance between the perpetrator and the victim. The perpetrator typically holds more power whether through organizational authority, social influence, or other advantages allowing them to repeatedly target the victim without facing immediate consequences (Einarsen, et al., 2011). This power imbalance reinforces the victim's sense of helplessness and entrapment, contributing to long-term psychological damage (Leymann, 1996). In workplaces with authoritarian leadership styles, bullying behaviors are more likely to flourish, as these environments often normalize or even encourage power-based exploitation (Branch, Ramsay, & Barker, 2013).

In Nigerian healthcare settings, this power dynamic is particularly prevalent. Senior nurses or administrators often hold substantial authority over junior staff, and the hierarchical structure of Nigerian hospitals can exacerbate bullying. For example, junior nurses may be subjected to intimidation or belittling by more experienced nurses or supervisors. These dynamics not only create an atmosphere of fear but also discourage

victims from speaking out, as they feel powerless to challenge the authority of their seniors.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Job Demand Control (JDC)

The Job Demand-Control (JDC), originally proposed by Robert Karasek in 1979, is one of the most widely recognized theories in occupational health psychology. It provides a framework for understanding the relationship between job demands, the level of control or decision-making latitude employees have, and the subsequent psychological outcomes, particularly job strain and stress-related behaviors. The Job Demand Control (JDC) model by Karasek (1979) emphasized the interaction between job demand and the degree of control employee have over their work tasks. Job demands refers to the physical and psychological pressures associated with the job such as the workload, time pressures and emotional labour while job control refers to the autonomy available to workers (Karasek 1979).

The model suggest that job strain is the highest when job demands are high and job control is low. However, when employees have a greater control, even higher demands do not necessarily result in strain (Karasek & Theorell 1990). Exposure to workplace bullying may also be more pronounced among employees with low job control, because having poor influence on one's own work may be associated with negative work characteristics, like for instance role conflict (Note-laers, et al., 2010 cited in Francioli, 2014), having the potential to increase the individual risk of being subjected to negative behaviour.

The JDC model offers an explanatory framework for understanding the conditions under which workplace bullying may occur. High job demands, such as heavy workloads and emotional strain, create stressful environments that can escalate interpersonal conflicts, leading to bullying behaviors (Einarsen, et al., 2020). Research indicates that individuals in high-strain jobs are more likely to experience workplace bullying due to the imbalance between job demands and control (Hauge, et al., 2010). Moreover, the JDC model has been linked to job burnout, a common consequence of prolonged exposure to high job demands and low control (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

Burnout has been identified as a mediator in the relationship between high-strain jobs and workplace bullying, particularly in healthcare settings (Salin & Hoel, 2021). When nurses experience burnout due to overwhelming demands, they are more susceptible to bullying behaviors, both as victims and perpetrators. This model is particularly relevant in the healthcare sector, where nurses often face high demands combined with limited control over their working conditions, making them vulnerable to negative psychological and physiological outcomes (Geuens, et al., 2020).

According to Baillien, et al, (2011), workplace bullying represents a social behavioural strain signalling the presence of adverse psychosocial working conditions, among which also high job demands and low job control may play a significant role. In particular, these authors maintained that a significant association between the JDC model and a higher probability of being subjected to workplace bullying may occur because

high job demands and low job control may impinge on employees' resources, and thus make them more likely to become an "easy target" of negative behaviours.

For instance, when confronted with high demands in the form of elevated time pressure, employees may more easily become targets in two ways: their need to raise efforts to keep up with the workload may eventually increase their stress and wear out their personal resources, while also restricting the time they have available to effectively manage emerging conflicts and invest in supportive relations at work (Francioli, 2014). The JDC model highlights the critical need for balance between job demands and control to safeguard nurses' well-being. In practice, enhancing job control through greater autonomy, participation in decision-making, and flexibility can mitigate the negative effects of high job demands, thereby reducing the risk of workplace bullying and improving overall job satisfaction (Laschinger & Fida, 2014).

A modified version of the JDC model, the Job Demand-Control-Support (JDCS) model, incorporates social support as a third dimension. According to this extended model, social support from supervisors and colleagues can buffer the negative impact of high demands and low control (Johnson & Hall, 1988). This is especially relevant in nursing, where collegial support plays a crucial role in reducing job strain and fostering a supportive work environment (Bakker, et al., 2021). Studies have shown that nurses who receive adequate support from their peers and supervisors are less likely to experience workplace bullying, as supportive environments help diffuse stress and conflict (Hauge, et al., 2011).

Recent research has expanded the JDC model by integrating it with other theories, such as the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014). While the JDC model focuses on job demands and control, the JD-R model extends this by considering job resources, such as support, feedback, and opportunities for development, as critical factors that influence employee well-being and performance. In this extended framework, workplace bullying can be viewed as a depletion of resources, where the absence of adequate job control and support increases the likelihood of bullying behaviors, particularly in high-demand environments like healthcare (Nielsen et al., 2016). The insights provided by the JDC model underscore the importance of organizational interventions aimed at reducing job demands and increasing job control to prevent workplace bullying and promote nurse well-being. Implementing strategies such as job redesign, workload management, and empowerment initiatives can help create healthier work environments where nurses feel in control of their tasks, thereby reducing stress and preventing the onset of bullying behaviors (Van den Tooren & De Jonge, 2010).

Furthermore, fostering a culture of social support can act as a protective factor, buffering the negative effects of high demands on nurses' mental health and reducing the incidence of workplace bullying (Salin, 2021). This theory captures how imbalance between demands and control can lead to heightened stress, creating a fertile ground for bullying behaviours to thrive.

Empirical Review

Empirical studies have shown that nurses frequently experience bullying in their workplaces. Dasci and Çamaloğlu (2016) investigated the role of organizational silence in perpetuating workplace bullying in healthcare setting. The study entails a Cross-sectional study of 400 healthcare workers in Turkey, using a validated organizational silence scale and the Negative Acts Questionnaire (NAQ). The findings of the study indicate that Fear of retaliation and lack of grievance mechanisms were significant predictors of organizational silence. However, it was concluded that encouraging open communication and implementing reporting systems can help mitigate workplace bullying.

Rodriguez-Muñoz et al. (2015) explore the relationship between workplace bullying and depression in a longitudinal study. 350 healthcare workers, including nurses, participated in surveys over 12 months. Depression was assessed using the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). The Findings shows that bullying significantly predicted depressive symptoms, including fatigue, sadness, and irritability. Participants exposed to chronic bullying reported higher depression scores. In Conclusion, Workplace bullying has long-term mental health impacts, emphasizing the need for early intervention and support mechanisms.

Hauge et al. (2010) examine the psychological effects of workplace bullying, with a focus on negative affectivity. A cross-sectional study of 500 healthcare employees in Norway using the Negative Acts Questionnaire (NAQ) and measures of negative affectivity. Findings of the study shows that victims of bullying experienced heightened negative emotions, including anger and frustration. Bullying indirectly influenced professional relationships and productivity through its impact on emotional states. The study concludes that addressing workplace bullying requires recognizing its emotional toll on employees and creating supportive environments.

Research by Johnson and Rea (2009) in the United States provides further evidence of the high prevalence of workplace bullying among nurses. Their study found that nurses who experienced bullying reported higher levels of job dissatisfaction, emotional exhaustion, and intent to leave their positions. The authors argued that workplace bullying in healthcare is a global phenomenon that requires urgent attention, given its potential to harm both staff well-being and patient care quality.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized *Ex-Post Facto* Design which is suitable for investigating variables where manipulation is not ethical and particularly appropriate for examining the influence of pre-existing conditions. The independent variables in the study was Organizational Silence. The Dependent variable was Workplace Bullying.

Area of Study

This study was carried out in six selected healthcare centers located in South-West Nigeria, specifically in Lagos, Oyo, and Osun States. These three states were selected using purposive sampling to capture the diversity of healthcare environments within the

region. In each state, one public hospital and one private hospital will be selected to ensure representation of diverse organizational contexts. The selection of hospitals was made to consider factors such as size, healthcare infrastructure, and geographical location. This approach ensures the study captures workplace dynamics across various institutional settings.

Population of the Study

The target population defines the units for which the results of the survey are intended to be generalized (Lyell, 2018). The population of this study comprises of nurses working in selected healthcare centers in three states across South-West Nigeria: Lagos, Oyo, and Osun States. These states were selected due to their diverse healthcare systems, which include a mix of public and private healthcare facilities and represent a significant portion of Nigeria's hospital workforce.

This focus on nurses is deliberate, as they are frontline healthcare providers who face high levels of work-related stress, making them particularly vulnerable to workplace bullying. Additionally, nurses play a vital role in healthcare delivery. The inclusion of both public and private hospitals ensures a comprehensive understanding of workplace bullying, as these settings often differ in organizational structures and workplace dynamics.

Sample Size and Sample Techniques

The study made use of random sampling techniques to select hospitals from the public and private hospitals in Lagos, Oyo and Osun States. This approach ensures that the sample is representative of the different types of healthcare centers. The sample size for this study was determined using the Taro Yamane's formula.

Clearly, the total sample size for the study, based on the Taro Yamane formula, is 622 nurses from selected public and private hospitals in Lagos, Oyo, and Osun states. This sample size will ensure that the study has adequate statistical power to detect significant effect. and ensures the generalizability of the findings across the target population of nurses in South-West Nigeria.

Method of Data Collection

A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from nurses in the selected states of Lagos, Oyo, and Osun. The questionnaire was designed to capture detailed information on workplace bullying and personality characteristics. The questionnaire was made up of three (3) sections, namely Section A (Socio-Demographic Characteristics), Section B measured organizational silence and Section C was (designed to assess Workplace Bullying. The copies of the questionnaire were administered in person to the selected nurses with the assistance of trained research assistants.

3.6 Research Instrument

The study utilized a structured questionnaire as the primary data collection instrument. A structured questionnaire is a quantitative data tool that allows respondents the opportunity to express their independent opinions on various elements of the study variables (Selara, 2016). To respond to the research questions and test the hypotheses, a specially designed questionnaire will be employed (Nwosu & Uffoh, 2015). The questionnaire

consists of nine (9) sections, each designed to measure different variables related to the study. The sections are:

Section A: Socio-Demographic Characteristics:

This section gathered basic demographic information from respondents, including gender, age, marital status, educational status, job status and work experience.

Section D: This section uses the Organizational Silence Scale by Daşcı and Necati Çamaloğlu, (2016) to measure employees' silence behaviors within an organization. Organizational silence occurs when employees withhold concerns, opinions, or ideas, often due to fear of negative consequences or a lack of trust in the organization. The scale contains 35 items categorized into several types of silence, such as acquiescent silence, defensive silence, pro-social silence, fear-based silence, and silence due to indifference. Items are rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5).

Section C: This section measured workplace bullying using a 21-item Workplace Bullying Scale. The scale measures both person-related and work-related bullying behaviors, with responses rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Never to 5 = Daily). The scale has demonstrated good reliability, with Cronbach's alpha of 0.87 for the overall scale and 0.77 for the two subscales.

Administration of Research Instrument

Before the distribution of the research instruments, a briefing session was held with the supervisors or heads of departments of the selected healthcare centers to explain the objectives of the study, the importance of the nurses' participation, and to address any concerns regarding confidentiality and the use of data.

This session will help ensure full cooperation and clear communication about the study's purpose and the ethical handling of data.

The questionnaires will then be distributed to the participants during their work shifts. Nurses will be given flexibility to complete the questionnaires at their convenience, minimizing any potential stress or time constraints that could affect their responses. By allowing nurses to complete the questionnaires during their shifts and at their own pace, we aim to improve the quality of the data collected while respecting the participants' time and workload.

Methods of Data Analysis

The study made use both the descriptive and inferential statistics for data analysis. The descriptive statistics was used to provide some summary information on the data collected, particularly the personal information associated with the respondents of the study such as gender, age, marital status and work experience. The inferential statistics was adopted to test the stated hypotheses. Specifically, hypothesis one will be analyzed using multiple regression while hypothesis two to eight will be analyzed using regression. All the hypotheses will be tested at 5 percent level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 were used to run the data.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter deals with the results of the study. It involved the descriptive analysis of the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents and test of stated hypotheses using regression analysis.

4.1 Socio - Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Table 4.1

Distribution of Respondents by Demographic Factors

Characteristics	Variable	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Sex	Male	67	16.0
	Female	353	84.0
	Total	420	100.0
		Frequency	Percentage(%)
20-24yrs		69	16.4
Age Group 25-29yrs		63	15.0
30-39yrs		101	24.0
40-44yrs		136	32.4
45yrs and above		51	12.1
Total		420	100.0
		Frequency	Percentage(%)
Educational Qualification	OND/Diploma/NCE	113	15.8
	HND/First Degree	171	69.5
	Postgraduate Diploma	36	
	Masters Degree	100	10.7
	Total	420	100.0
		Frequency	Percentage(%)
Marital Status	Single	64	17.2
	Married	356	76.8
	Total	420	100.0
		Frequency	Percentage(%)
Religion	Christianity	188	44.8
	Islam	232	55.2
	Total	420	100
		Frequency	Percent
	0 - 4 years	58	13.8
Working Experience	5 - 9yrs	126	59.4
	10 – 14yrs	107	13.8
	15 – 19yrs	87	2.7
	20yrs and above	42	0.3
	Total	420	100

Authors' Field Survey (2025).

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

HYPOTHESIS ONE

Organizational silence will not significantly influence workplace bullying experience among nurses in

hospital in South-West, Nigeria. The hypothesis was tested by Linear regression. The results are shown in tables 2 3 and 4

Table 2

A Summary Table of Linear Regression Showing Contributions of Organizational Silence to Workplace Bullying

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.463 ^a	.215	.213	5.100

a. Predictors: (Constant), ORGANIZATIONAL SILENCE

The model summary table (Table 2) presents an R-squared (R²) value of 0.215. This value indicates that the organizational silence variable showed a relatively moderate influence on workplace bullying among nurses in hospitals in South-west. The R-squared value of 0.215 suggests that the models collectively predicted

approximately 22% of the variability observed in workplace bullying. This implies that around 22% of the variance in workplace bullying among nurses in hospitals in South-West Nigeria levels can be anticipated through organizational silence factor encompassed in the study's models.

Table 3

A Summary Table Showing of Linear Regression Showing the F ratio of the Predictive Influence of Organizational Silence on Workplace Bullying among Nurses in Hospitals in South-West Nigeria

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	2971.665	1	2971.665	114.258	.000 ^b
Residual	10871.535	418	26.008		
Total	13843.200	419			

a. Dependent Variable: WORKPLACE BULLYING

b. Predictors: (Constant), ORGANIZATIONAL SILENCE

The results displayed in Table 3 indicated a significant prediction of workplace bullying by the organizational silence variable. The F-statistic of $F(1, 418) = 114.258$, with a p-value less than 0.05, signifies that the

overall regression model demonstrates a high level of statistical significance in terms of its goodness of fit. This is supported by the fact that the calculated F-statistic (F_{cal}) surpasses the critical F-value (F_{tab}).

Table 4

A Summary Table of Linear Regression Showing the Individual Contribution Organizational Silence to Workplace Bullying

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	42.326	2.582		16.391	.000
ORGANIZATIONAL SILENCE	.232	.022	.463	10.689	.000

a. Dependent Variable: WORKPLACE BULLYING

Table 4. presents the individual contribution of the predictor variable. Specifically, organizational silence variable exhibited a moderate contribution with a Beta coefficient of .463, accompanied by a p-value less than .05 and a t-value of 10.689. This contribution is statistically significant in relation to workplace bullying. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted, leading to the conclusion that work stress significantly influenced workplace bullying among nurses in hospitals in South-West Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, it is thereby concluded that:

- Work stress significantly influenced workplace bullying experience among nurses in hospital in South-West, Nigeria.

IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A very effective strategy to address workplace bullying is generating its awareness. Existing literature supported that raising awareness about bullying is effective to escape from after effects (Salin, 2013; Vartia & Leka, 2011). Therefore, information and attitude campaigns would help both managers and employees recognize bullying behavior and understand their consequences.

Secondly, periodically personality development training must also be provided to all employees serving all levels which will help them to groom their personalities and especially for senior employees which will help them to better survive in this growing diverse environment.

Lastly, practitioners should help business institu-

tions, while developing course content for business students to design a course based on bullying awareness and protection against bullying. Existing literature also supported the need for involving practitioners seeking inspiration to more developed disciplines to identify empirically evaluated intervention methods against bullying (Cassidy et al., 2019).

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